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Journal of Cranio-Maxillo-Facial Surgery

journal homepage: www.jcmfs.com

"Injectable platelet-rich fibrin for modelling of mandibular lower border defects in bilateral sagittal split osteotomy"

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Platelet-rich fibrin
 Orthognathic surgery
 Bone defect

ABSTRACT

Despite the remarkable progress in virtual surgical planning in the last few decades, which has made orthognathic surgery results more precise and predictable, there remains an unforeseeable risk of developing mandibular lower border defects after bilateral sagittal split osteotomy (BSSO). These defects can cause visible and palpable irregularities of the lower border of the mandible, thereby worsening the surgical result. The study aimed to evaluate the benefit of injectable platelet-rich fibrin (i-PRF) for contour defect modelling in orthognathic surgery in comparison to conventional orthognathic surgery. i-PRF was used to fill the osteotomy gap in BSSO aiming to stimulate bone tissue formation and reduce the risk of mandibular lower border defect formation. Additionally, the correlation between the concentration of the most important growth factors and interleukins in i-PRF and clinical outcomes of different patients was investigated. Also, the antibacterial activity of i-PRF was tested. Cone-beam computed tomography analysis demonstrated a statistically significant increase of bone volume in the BSSO vertical osteotomy gap when i-PRF was applied during surgery. The findings of the study support the use of an autologous biomaterial for BSSO, utilizing a simple preparation technique and application, while also contributing to a deeper understanding of i-PRF content and properties. Study protocol published in ISRCTN10296235 registry <https://doi.org/10.1186/ISRCTN10296235>.

1. Introduction

Bilateral sagittal split osteotomy (BSSO) is the most commonly performed jaw surgery used to achieve stable class I functional occlusion and to establish a harmonious maxillofacial profile and proper facial aesthetics (Monson, 2013; Agbaje et al., 2016; Verweij et al., 2016). This type of mandibular osteotomy allows to correct horizontal mandibular excess, deficiency, asymmetry, and mandibular advancement or setback

(Monson, 2013). Three-dimensional treatment planning for orthognathic surgery has become essential to enable more precise and predictable surgical results, however, the risk of several complications due to the complexity of the procedure remains. Some of the most common complications associated with BSSO are bleeding, postoperative infection, neurosensory disturbances, unfavorable fracture patterns, malposition of the proximal segment, malocclusion, relapse, condylar malposition, condylar resorption, condylar remodelling, avascular

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcms.2025.07.018>

Received 7 February 2025; Received in revised form 11 July 2025; Accepted 19 July 2025

Available online 5 August 2025

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necrosis, and worsening of temporomandibular joint symptoms (Monson, 2013; Spaey et al., 2005). Surgical wound infection after BSSO is a significant problem due to the inevitable direct contact with oral flora. To avoid infection-associated complications the prophylactic use of antibiotics, amoxicillin-clavulanate, is indicated in the perioperative period (Spaey et al., 2005). However, the prophylactic use of antibiotics is debatable due to concerns about spreading resistance and the principles of antibiotic stewardship. A less common, but no less important complication, is a bone defect at the inferior border of the mandible near the vertical osteotomy site which occurs due to insufficient bone healing. These inferior border defects compromise the aesthetic result of the surgery with palpable and visible irregularities on the lower border of the mandible resulting in patient concerns (Verweij et al., 2016; Agbaje et al., 2013). According to Verweij et al. (2017) there are several risk factors for osseous inferior border defects after BSSO including large mandibular advancement, increased clockwise rotation of the occlusal plane, cranial rotation of the proximal segment, and split originating in the lingual cortex. Given the limited self-regeneration capacity, interventions to stimulate tissue formation are needed. Although various biomaterials to fill the osteotomy gap or to stimulate bone tissue regeneration are available, all of them exhibit limitations, such as increased surgical time and costs or a higher risk of infection (Miron et al., 2024). As a result, achieving adequate healing of bone defects is challenging, therefore, the development of effective alternatives is required.

Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) is a fully autologous preparation from a patient's peripheral blood without anticoagulants and any other biochemical additive (Choukroun et al., 2001). It is widely used by clinicians in dentistry, oral and maxillofacial surgery, dermatology, plastic and regenerative surgery, orthopaedics, ophthalmology and neurology (Miron et al., 2024; Micko et al., 2023; Cencerska-Heryc et al., 2022; Fan et al., 2020). It has also been introduced to neurosurgery, as well as in ear, nose, and throat medicine (Theys et al., 2018; Shukla et al., 2020). PRF forms a 3D structure containing a supraphysiological concentration of leukocytes and platelets, making it unique (Al-Hamed et al., 2019) with well-established regenerative potential and immunological activity (Karde et al., 2017; Jasmine et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2017; Herrera-Vizcaíno et al., 2019; Mudalal et al., 2019). Platelets are megakaryocyte cell fragments and constitute the dominant component of PRF. They contain α , δ , and λ granules and, upon activation, release more than 300 different proteins in high concentration, thus contributing to tissue regeneration (Pochini et al., 2016). α granules constitute the main reservoir of growth factors such as transforming growth factor beta (TGF β), platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF), vascular endothelium growth factor (VEGF), fibroblast growth factor (FGF), epidermal growth factor (EGF), hepatocyte growth factor (HGF) and insulin-like growth factor (IGF) (Jalowiec et al., 2016; Blair and Flaumenhaft, 2009). Platelet-released angiogenic activators promote blood vessel permeability, endothelial cell and fibroblast cell recruitment, growth, and proliferation, thus play a role in angiogenesis and inflammation modulation (Blair and Flaumenhaft, 2009). Besides platelets, PRF contains high concentrations of leukocytes and immune cytokines such as interleukins (IL1, IL4, IL6, IL8), and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF α) acting as modulators in the tissue healing process (Gurtner et al., 2008; Choukroun and Ghanaati, 2018; Dohan et al., 2006). Different types of PRF can be obtained by adjusting the relative centrifugation forces (RCF) during material preparation. Specifically, low-speed centrifugation in the preparation protocol yields injectable PRF (i-PRF), which has a higher cell count and growth factor concentration compared to PRF prepared using higher centrifugation forces (Choukroun and Ghanaati, 2018).

Due to the risk of developing a mandibular lower border defect in patients after BSSO surgery, the application of an appropriate biomaterial at the vertical osteotomy site to mitigate this issue may be worth of investigating. The excellent characteristics of PRF and the remarkable clinical results in various applications make it a promising potential

solution.

Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of i-PRF in patients for contour defect modelling in orthognathic surgery, comparing it to conventional orthognathic surgery. To estimate bone tissue healing in the vertical osteotomy sites after BSSO, bone tissue volume measurements were carried out in the potential contour defect sites. Risk factors contributing to the development of mandibular lower border defects were also evaluated and considered. Furthermore, to investigate the role of i-PRF composition, the concentrations of selected growth factors, EGF, VEGF, PDGF, TGF- β 1, and IL-8, in i-PRF samples from test group patients were measured. This analysis aimed to investigate the correlation between these growth factors, cytokines, and clinical outcomes across the patient group. Additionally, its antibacterial activity was characterized to describe the potential of using i-PRF as an effective local antibacterial agent.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Trial design, report, and implementation

A randomized controlled clinical trial was conducted. This study adhered to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. A study protocol was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Riga Stradins University, approval No. 6-1/09/8. The protocol has been published and is available at ISRCTN10296235 <https://doi.org/10.1186/ISRCTN10296235> (Micko et al., 2024). The study was implemented according to the published protocol and reported following the CONSORT recommendations (Schulz et al., 2010).

2.2. Patient selection and allocation

All adult patients diagnosed with dentofacial deformities and scheduled for BSSO surgery at Riga Stradins University Institute of Stomatology and Pauls Stradins Clinical University Hospital between 2020 and 2023 were informed about and considered for participation in the study. Patients with any uncontrolled chronic disease, regular medication intake, nicotine and alcohol abuse were excluded. Each patient was also tested for serum vitamin D levels where a level of less than 35 ng/mL was considered insufficient to proceed. Study participants were randomly divided into the study group and the control group using the block randomization method. Written consent for participation in this research was obtained from each patient.

2.3. Blood collection and platelet-rich fibrin preparation for laboratory testing

Peripheral venous blood samples were collected from each study group patient 24–48 h before their BSSO surgery. Whole blood from the patients was obtained using 10 mL i-PRF plastic tubes (PROCESS FOR PRF, 06000, Nice, France) without anti-coagulants, which were immediately placed into a centrifuge ("PRF DUO Quattro", Nice, France) and centrifuged at room temperature for 700 revolutions per minute (rpm) with relative centrifugal force (RFC) 60 g for 3 or 4 min for females and males, respectively. After the centrifugation, the upper layer of processed blood (around 1 mL) from each tube was transferred into separate 2 mL tubes and stored at -80°C for 4–6 months. Upon first need, frozen i-PRF samples were thawed on ice at room temperature, split in aliquots, the required number of samples were used, and the remaining aliquots were stored at -80°C until further analysis.

2.4. Blood collection and platelet-rich fibrin preparation for clinical application

During the surgery, before the osteosynthesis of the mandible, peripheral venous blood samples were obtained using four i-PRF plastic tubes and centrifuged as described above. The upper layer of processed

blood, which is i-PRF, was transferred into a metal surgical bowl and maintained for 30 min until the end of the coagulation process. i-PRF changed from a liquid into a gel-like state and was ready for clinical application.

2.5. Bilateral sagittal split osteotomy and injectable platelet-rich fibrin application

The BSSO procedures were carried out on all patients according to the same surgical technique and protocol performed by 3 professional maxillofacial surgeons. For hemostatic purposes, infiltration of a local anesthetic solution was performed 10 min prior to the surgery. The solution was administered into soft tissue submucosally and subperiostally at the incision site, as well as laterally to the anterior border of the ascending ramus, medially and laterally to the retromolar area, and buccally at the molar region. Additionally, bilateral inferior alveolar nerve (IAN) blocks were performed to achieve hemostasis. The vestibular “V-shaped” incision from the distal part of the second molar to the medial margin of the lower second premolar through all tissue layers and periosteum is done and the anterior border of the mandible is stripped for access to the medial ramus. Then followed subperiosteal dissection with the identification of the position of the lingula and mandibular foramen. The osteotomy was carried out according to the modified Hunsuck technique (Böckmann et al., 2015). Careful and controlled splitting of the mandible was performed followed by IAN release and adjustment of the bone fragments so that the distal fragment was free and passive. The distal fragment was attached to the upper jaw using a splint and wires in position according to the surgical plan. The proximal segment was positioned using bi-vector seating of the condyles. Osteosynthesis of the mandible was implemented with 2.0 mm miniplates, miniscrews, and one positioning screw in the retro-mandibular fragment. For test group patients, before the closure of the surgical wound, a previously prepared i-PRF gel in equal volume was placed in the gap between the proximal and distal fragments of the mandible at the vertical osteotomy site in the right and left side of the mandible. No i-PRF or other materials were used for the control group. In both groups, the surgical wounds were closed by layers using absorbable surgical material without drainage. No bone substitutes were used in any surgery.

2.6. Cone-beam computed tomography evaluation

All patients underwent a yearlong post-surgical observation during which they had cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) examinations done at two time points: 7–12 days after surgery and at the one-year follow-up mark. All CBCT scans were performed on the same device (i-CAT Next generation, Kavo Dental GmbH, Warthausen, Germany)

with the following parameters: 120 kVp, 5 mA, 4 s exposure time, 0.3 mm voxel size, 160 × 130 mm (diameter × height) field of view (FOV). All examinations were stored on a local database in DICOM format and were imported into Mimics (version 25.0, Materialise NV, Leuven, Belgium) for further processing. Initially, the CBCT scans for each patient were superimposed between one another by using a voxel-based approach with the distal segment of the first examination as the reference region. The first time point (7–12 days after surgery) was used to measure the size of the gap between the proximal and distal mandibular fragments and the cortical thickness, on each side (Fig. 1).

These measurements were done on a reconstruction, based on a curve parallel to the axial midline of the mandible. The first slice, when moving in an internal direction from the chin area, where both the mandibular segments could be seen was used to measure the gap size as a straight line parallel to the lower border of the proximal mandibular segment. The cortical thickness was measured on the proximal fragment as a line perpendicular to the lower border of the proximal segment in a slice where identifying the borders of the cortex was the least ambiguous (Fig. 1).

In the CBCT examinations the mandible was segmented using thresholding, with the lower threshold value adjusted individually for each patient. This approach helped minimising artifacts while also reducing the need for extensive manual corrections. After thresholding, manual editing was carried out, and any internal gaps were filled to finalise the segmentation. These segmentations were used to determine the fracture pattern of the osteotomy and to assess the postoperative position of the proximal segment. The pattern of lingual fracture was classified as either a type I or a type II split (Verweij et al., 2017) (Fig. 2).

Any osteotomies resulting in a bad split were documented. In the meta-analysis by Verweij et al. (2016) the postoperative position of the proximal segment was classified as a good anatomical position of the proximal segment, slight rotation of the proximal segment of less than one cortical thickness, or significant rotation of the proximal segment of more than one cortical thickness. The fragments could be deemed to be in a good anatomical position when the lower border of the proximal and distal mandibular fragments were aligned. They were considered to be in slight rotation when the lower border of the proximal and distal mandibular fragments was misaligned by a distance up to or equal to the cortical thickness. Significant rotation was noted when the lower border of the proximal and distal mandibular fragments was misaligned by a distance greater than the cortical thickness (Fig. 2). The mandible from the one-year follow-up examination was segmented by the same approach described previously, although the same lower thresholding value was used as in the previous time point.

To obtain the volumetric changes between the two time points a Boolean subtraction was done between the two segmentations. Subtraction of the one-year follow-up model from the immediate post-

Fig. 1. CBCT measurements. (a) The measurements of gap size between proximal and distal mandibular fragments on the right and left side after BSSO and osteosynthesis are indicated by the red lines in the selected slice of the reconstruction. (b) The measurement of cortical thickness on the right side after BSSO and osteosynthesis is indicated by the green line in the selected slice of the reconstruction.

Fig. 2. Risk factors for mandibular lower border defect development. (a) The pattern of lingual fracture - type I. (b) The pattern of lingual fracture - type II. (c, d, e) The proximal segment postoperative position. (c) Good anatomical position of the proximal segment. (d) Slight rotation of the proximal segment. (e) Significant rotation of the proximal segment.

operative model was deemed to be indicative of bone remodelling and resorption while the inverse was deemed indicative of bone formation. Any changes with regard to the teeth or fixation plates were excluded. To obtain volumetric values solely for the region where the gap was present between the two mandibular fragments, two planes representing the said gap were created – one parallel to the osteotomy line of the distal mandibular fragment and one parallel to the osteotomy line of the proximal mandibular fragment. These planes were then moved 1 cm parallel to the axial outer border of the mandible (Fig. 3) and used to trim the segmentations to obtain the value for localized relative bone volume change (Fig. 4).

The difference between the increase in bone volume and the volume of bone resorption was defined as the net bone volume change. Measurements that could not be obtained from the CBCT examinations - preoperative occlusal planes and postoperative occlusal planes - were extracted from the orthognathic surgical plan for each corresponding patient.

The segmentation from the one-year post-surgery examination was used by 2 observers - experienced oral and maxillo-facial surgeons (G.S., A.D.) - for visual mandibular lower border evaluation to consider whether there was a visual defect within the lower border of the mandible where the gap between the fragments was present previously (Fig. 5).

Fig. 3. The planes used for determining the area for measuring the bone volumetric changes within the region of the vertical osteotomy.

2.7. i-PRF preparation for enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA)

To determine the concentration of growth factors and interleukins in each patient, frozen i-PRF samples were slowly thawed on ice, vortexed, placed at room temperature, and observed for 30 min until clot formation (Fig. 6). Tubes with clotted i-PRF were shortly spun to separate clots and supernatant. The clot supernatants from each patient's samples were used for the ELISA assays.

2.8. Protein quantification in i-PRF with ELISA

The supernatant around clots was used to quantify the protein content (EGF, VEGF, PDGF, TGFβ1, IL8) of the sample by using ELISA. Commercially available ELISA (DuoSet, R&D Systems, Abingdon, UK and Merck KGaA, Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany) were used according to manufacturer's protocol to quantify EGF (DEG00, assay range 3.91–250 pg/mL), VEGF (DVE00, assay range 15.6–1000 pg/mL), PDGF (DBB00, assay range 31.2–2000 pg/mL), TGFβ1 (RAB0460, assay range 16.38–4000 pg/mL) and IL-8 (D8000C, assay range 31.2–2000 pg/mL). Absorbance was measured at 450 nm with a reference wavelength of 540 nm using Tecan Infinite 200 Pro plate reader (Tecan Group Ltd, Mannedorf, Switzerland). All samples were tested in duplicates. Standards supplied with each kit were used to generate standard curves. Absorbance from wells containing only medium was set as the blank and subtracted from the test well readouts.

2.9. Anti-bacterial testing using agar diffusion method

To test the anti-bacterial activity of i-PRF collected from test group patients a bacterial suspensions of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (*K.pneumoniae*) reference culture (ATCC 10031), *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S.aureus*) reference culture (ATCC 25923), *Porphyromonas gingivalis* (*P.gingivalis*) reference culture (ATCC 33277) and *Fusobacterium nucleatum* (*F.nucleatum*) reference culture (ATCC 25586) were prepared with an optic density of 0.5 according to the McFarland standard. Bacterial suspensions of *K.pneumoniae* and *S.aureus* were inoculated on Mueller Hinton agar (MHA) (Oxoid, UK) and respectively *P.gingivalis* and *F.nucleatum* suspensions were inoculated on enriched blood agar (Oxoid, UK). All collected i-PRF aliquots were thawed on ice at room temperature until liquid state. Eppendorf tubes containing i-PRF were vortexed and then 50 μL of i-PRF were pipetted on agar plates in 3 different places. Further MHA plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h and Enriched blood agars were under anaerobic conditions for 5 days at 37 °C (Oxoid, AnaeroGen, 7–15 % CO₂). Agar diffusion method results were evaluated by measuring zones of inhibition (ZOI) around the i-PRF.

Fig. 4. The visualisation of localized bone volume change. (a) The bone volume gain (green) on top of the 7–12 days post-surgery segmentation on the left side of the mandible. (b) The bone resorption volume (red) on top of the year post-surgery segmentation on the left side of the mandible.

Fig. 5. The presence of a mandibular lower border defect. (a) Superimposed segmentations of the 7–12 days and one-year post-surgery examinations. (b) The presence of a mandibular lower border defect in the segmentation at one-year post-surgery examination.

Fig. 6. (a) Blood collection and centrifugation. (b) i-PRF preparation and storage. (c) i-PRF sample preparation for ELISA. (d) i-PRF testing using ELISA assay.

2.10. Statistical analysis of data

The data distribution was assessed by inspection of the normal Q-Q

plot and with the Shapiro-Wilk test. For normally distributed data, mean values and standard deviations were reported. In contrast, the median and interquartile range (IQR) was used to summarize non-normally

distributed data. Nominal data was described by frequencies and percentages. Data homogeneity was assessed with the Levene test. The dependent samples *t*-test was conducted to assess if the means of continuous dependent variables gap size, bone gain, bone resorption/remodelling and net bone volume change differed significantly between the left and right side. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test, a nonparametric alternative, was used for non-normally distributed data. The independent samples *t*-test was conducted to test the difference of gap size, bone gain, bone resorption, net bone volume changes between the test and control groups and between the types of procedure. Protein concentrations were compared between repetitions and genders. The Mann-Whitney *U* test, a nonparametric alternative, was used for non-normally distributed data. The chi-squared test of homogeneity or the Fisher's test was used to compare the fracture pattern and bad split presence between the test and control groups, as well as between the type of procedure. To account for the potential influence of risk factors (gap size, fracture pattern, bad split presence and proximal segment postoperative position presence) on net bone volume change, a linear regression analysis was performed comparing the test and control groups. The relationship between protein concentrations, age, and net bone volume change was assessed by Spearman's rank correlation test. To assess whether protein concentrations were uniformly distributed among patients, a Kolmogorov-Smirnov test with Lilliefors correction, using 10,000 Monte Carlo simulations, was performed. To calculate the level of agreement among two raters assessing presence of mandibular lower border defect in CBCT segmentation one-year post-surgery, the Cohen's Kappa was used. Statistical data analysis was performed with Jamovi (v.2.5). The results were considered statistically significant when the *p* value < 0.05.

3. Results

Overall, the study included 54 patients – 27 in the test group with the use of i-PRF and in the control group without the use of i-PRF in the surgery. Due to patient loss during follow up 19 patients were excluded. Finally, data was analysed for a total of 35 patients - 21 in the study group and 14 in the control group (Fig. 7). 18 of them were males and 17 were females. Patient ages ranged from 18 to 47 years, with a mean age of 25.8 ± 8.1 years. During the whole study period no complications were observed. All patients were satisfied with the surgical results. No postoperative skeletal relapse was observed in either the test group or the study group patients during the 1-year follow-up period. The power of analysis was 0.79 (79 %).

3.1. CBCT analysis

Comparison of the right and left sides of the BSSO revealed no statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$) in bone volume measurements at the vertical osteotomy site, as well as in the gap size. Therefore, data from both sides were merged and further analysed together. The BSSO lingual fracture pattern and the proximal segment postoperative position did not differ significantly between the test and control groups ($p > 0.05$), as well as between the BSSO combinations with other orthognathic surgeries ($p > 0.05$). Also, there was no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between the bone volume measurements in vertical osteotomy sites and BSSO combinations with other orthognathic surgeries. There was a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in occlusal plane rotation and net bone volume change between the test and control groups, with a moderate effect size (Table 1). However, after controlling for potential risk factors, net bone volume change at the vertical osteotomy site remained significantly different between groups ($p < 0.05$). The net bone volume change was 420 mm^3 (SD = 296) in the test group versus 223 mm^3 (SD = 230) in the control group. Moreover, a strong positive correlation was observed between net bone volume change and gap size in the regression model. For each 1 mm increase in gap size, net bone volume increased by 45.4 mm^3 .

Results from visual mandibular lower border evaluation at the one-year follow-up from 42 test group BSSO sites showed lower border defects in 13 sites (31 %), while 29 sites (69 %) did not. In the control group, of 28 BSSO sites lower border defects were identified in 9 sites (32 %), whereas 19 sites (68 %) exhibited a smooth mandibular lower border (Fig. 8). Cohen's kappa showed moderate agreement (74.3 %)

Table 1

The difference of risk factors and bone volume change between the test and control group.

Parameters	Test group	Control group	<i>p</i>	Effect size
Gap size (mm), median (Q1 – Q3)	3.5 (2.3–5.6)	2.9 (2.0–5.4)	0.412	NA
Occlusal plane rotation (°), mean (SD)	3.6 (2.7)	2.3 (1.8)	0.026	0.57
Bone resorption/remodelling (mm ³), median (Q1 – Q3)	242 (183–357)	266 (171–333)	0.914	NA
Net bone volume change (mm ³), mean (SD)	420 (296)	223 (230)	0.004	0.73

Note: NA – not applicable; SD – standard deviation; Q1-Q3 – the first and third quartiles.

Fig. 7. Consort flow diagram.

Fig. 8. The visualisation and comparison of bone formation and resorption in test and control group patients. (1a,2a,3a,4a) Test group patients 7 days post-surgery CBCT segmentation with marked bone volume gain (green) on top. (1b,2b,3b,4b) The bone resorption volume (red) on top of the year post-surgery segmentation from test group patient. (1c,2c,3c,4c) Mandibular lower border of test group patients CBCT segmentation year post-surgery. (5a,6a,7a,8a) Control group patient 7 days post-surgery CBCT segmentation with marked bone volume gain (green) on top. (5b,6b,7b,8b) The bone resorption volume (red) on top of the year post-surgery segmentation from control group patient. (5c,6c,7c,8c) Mandibular lower border of control group patients CBCT segmentation year post-surgery.

between the observers' decisions about whether there was a mandibular lower border defect, with a kappa value of 0.5 ($p = 0.007$), suggesting a reasonable level of consistency.

3.2. Growth factor pattern in i-PRF using ELISA immune assay

Peripheral blood samples were collected from 21 test group patients. Patients were aged from 18 to 47 years, with a mean age of 26.9 ± 8.4 years. 11 of them were males and 10 were females. Blood samples to prepare i-PRF were obtained 1–2 days before the surgery and frozen. ELISA test was performed in duplicates for each sample, with no differences detected in the technical duplicates ($p < 0.05$). All growth factors (EGF, VEGF, PDGF-BB, TGF β 1) quantified in i-PRF were found within the range of detection of their respective assays. TGF β 1 was found to be in the highest concentration in i-PRF compared to all tested growth factors, ranging from 4854.6 pg/mL to 37643.8 pg/mL (Fig. 9). IL8 was present with the lowest concentrations ranging from 16.8 pg/mL to 57.9 pg/mL. The results of a Kolmogorov-Smirnov test showed that TGF β 1 and IL8 do not follow a uniform distribution among patients, indicating that these protein concentrations vary significantly across the patient population ($p < 0.001$). Other proteins, PDGF-BB, EGF, and VEGF, were found to be in consistent concentrations among the patients of the test group. PDGF ranged between 2255.3 pg/mL and 6049.8 pg/mL. EGF and VEGF were found in the range from 323.8 pg/mL to 865.5 pg/mL and 166.6 pg/mL to 697.2 pg/mL, respectively.

Statistical analysis revealed a strongly significant positive correlation ($p < 0.001$) between the concentration of PDGF and EGF in i-PRF samples from different donors (Table 2). Furthermore, there was a

statistically significant moderate positive correlation ($p < 0.01$) between PDGF and TGF β 1, IL8 and EGF, IL8 and VEGF. The correlation between TGF β 1 and VEGF was statistically significant although moderately negative ($p < 0.05$). No correlation between protein concentration and donors' age was found, as well as data analysis did not reveal differences in protein concentration between males and females ($p > 0.05$). Furthermore, no significant correlation was found between protein concentrations and changes in net bone volume ($p > 0.05$). This suggests that specific protein concentration is not related to patient healing outcomes.

3.3. Antibacterial activity of i-PRF

Only one i-PRF sample, patient number 30 from the test group, demonstrated pronounced antibacterial activity against *S.aureus* showing a mean ZOI 24,8 mm. Other samples did not show an antibacterial effect against *S.aureus* or *K.pneumoniae*. No antibacterial activity was found against *P.gingivalis* and *F.nucleatum* indicated by the lack of any ZOI (Fig. 10).

4. Discussion

Orthognathic surgery is a highly technical and complex procedure that demands advanced skills from a craniomaxillofacial surgeon. The unique properties of PRF may be exploited in oral and maxillofacial surgery to improve outcomes and decrease the risk of several complications. PRF has been described for its high concentration of growth factors, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial activity, autologous origin, and

Fig. 9. (a, b, c, d, e) TGFβ1, IL8, PDGF-BB, EGF, VEGF concentration in i-PRF from 21 donors (marked corresponding to patient identification numbers).

Table 2

Associations between protein concentrations in i-PRF and net bone volume change of test group patients.

Variables	EGF (pg/mL)	VEGF (pg/mL)	TGFβ1 (pg/mL)	PDGF (pg/mL)	IL8 (pg/mL)
EGF (pg/mL)	–				
VEGF (pg/mL)	0.236	–			
TGFβ1 (pg/mL)	0.128	–0.426 **	–		
PDGF (pg/mL)	0.501 ***	0.095	0.366 *	–	
IL8 (pg/mL)	0.336 *	0.311 *	–0.167	0.032	–
Net bone volume change (mm ³)	0.405	0.240	–0.056	0.142	0.329

*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001.

ease of preparation (Miron et al., 2017a,b). In most reported cases, the clinical effect of PRF and its injectable version i-PRF have been described in minor surgeries such as teeth extraction, alveolar ridge preservation, dental implant placement, sinus lift surgery, and periodontal surgeries (Ye et al., 2024; Canellas et al., 2020; Suttapreyasri

and Leepong, 2013; Tabrizi et al., 2018; Cho et al., 2020; Hamzacebi et al., 2015). However, favorable effects, such as accelerated wound healing, improved soft tissue regeneration, enhanced bone regeneration, faster neurosensory recovery, and reduction of postoperative pain and swelling demonstrated by PRF in the last decades, made it attractive also for use in BSSO (Hegde et al., 2024; Micko et al., 2023).

This study demonstrated improved bone healing in the BSSO vertical osteotomy site by applying i-PRF compared to the control group. CBCT segmentation depicted a larger newly formed bone volume in the vertical osteotomy site of BSSO in patients who received i-PRF during the surgery. Specifically, the net bone volume change was 420 mm³ (SD = 296) in the test group versus 223 mm³ (SD = 230) in the control group, with a p-value of 0.004. However, despite the favorable effect of i-PRF, it could not be perceived as a preventive approach against the formation of mandibular lower border defects. The use of i-PRF it cannot confront various defect development risk factors, which may not even be completely predictable. Mandibular advancement (gap size in vertical osteotomy region) is described as the major risk factor among others (Verweij et al., 2016).

According to Agbaje et al. (2013), Cifuentes et al. (2018), Raffaini et al. (2020), the bone grafting in the BSSO osteotomy gap is

Fig. 10. Antibacterial activity of i-PRF against *K. pneumoniae* and *S. aureus* using agar diffusion method. (a) No ZOI is shown around i-PRF on the plate after incubation tested against *K.pneumoniae*. Areas of i-PRF sample placement were marked with dashed line. (b) Antibacterial activity of i-PRF against *S. aureus* showing ZOI.

recommended for large mandibular advancement starting from 10 mm. The results of meta-analysis by [da Hora Sales et al. \(2023\)](#) indicate the reduction in bone defect prevalence observed in the bone graft group. However, the success of bone grafting is controversial. For example, [van der Helm et al. \(2020\)](#) showed significantly lower mean height of lower border defect when a grafting material (Bio-Oss xenografts (Geistlich Pharma, Wolhusen, Switzerland) in combination with Tissucol fibrin glue (Baxter, Deerfield, IL, USA)) was used, but demonstrated negligible effect in cases with large mandibular fragment displacements (9.0–15.0 mm). Also, they did not observe the significant difference in lower border defect volume measurements. The bone grafting procedure is technically demanding due to limited direct visualisation, difficult graft placement, and evaluation of the optimal graft volume. Compared to other methods, the use of an i-PRF clot for filling the mandibular osteotomy gap offers straightforward material preparation and simpler application during surgery. Therefore, the use of i-PRF could be considered in cases with minor mandibular fragment movements. In contrast, bone grafting might be suggested for larger mandibular advancements. To avoid any bias due to a patient's excessive emphasis on the aesthetic aspect of the jawline, a radiographical visual analysis of the mandibular lower border was used in this study. While the volumetric analysis indicated increased bone regeneration in the test group, visual observations of lower border defects by two independent observers did not suggest a distinct advantage associated with the use of i-PRF. It should be noted that, despite the variety of lower border defect assessment techniques available, [van der Helm et al. \(2020\)](#) emphasize that no single method can be considered entirely definitive.

The choice of the growth factors and cytokines which were analysed in i-PRF (TGF β 1, PDGF, EGF, VEGF, and IL8) was because of their direct or indirect functional contribution to tissue regeneration, especially bone ([Yu et al., 2019](#); [Xu et al., 2020](#)). No correlation was found between net bone volume change and i-PRF protein composition in test group patients. This could be explained by the lack of remarkable differences in i-PRF content between different test group patients, whereas only TGF β 1 and IL8 concentrations varied among patients. However, the amount of growth factors in the biomaterial may also change during i-PRF preparation, material storage, freezing and thawing manipulations, or during the clotting time frame. For PRF characterization purposes, many authors are determining protein content and their concentration in PRF. Most authors measure protein release concentration in time from PRF clots to the cell media, and such methodology is widely described ([Miron et al., 2017a,b](#); [Fujioka-Kobayashi et al., 2017](#)). In this study, blood samples were obtained 1–2 days before surgery and prepared i-PRF samples were stored in a freezer to be able to analyse the protein content of the biomaterial from all patients simultaneously. As tested

biomaterial was frozen and thawed, protein release measurements could not have been used due to additional manipulation, which might have influenced cells and proteins within the material. For this reason, it was decided to use a supernatant around the clot of i-PRF for protein quantification using the ELISA assay. It should be acknowledged that the need to collect and freeze i-PRF samples causes further possible differences between fresh and frozen-thawed biomaterial. It should also be noted that the supernatant may not fully reflect the content of the i-PRF clot. Growth factors may interact in liquid i-PRF, its clot or supernatant. The supernatant indirectly describes abundant protein content in the i-PRF clot which is formed in initially liquid biomaterial after the coagulation process. Such methodology was chosen because of the biomaterials' clotting ability, thus possibly interfering with immunological processes during the ELISA test.

Despite the antibacterial activity already well-established for various types of PRF, it is mainly studied in vitro. ([Karde et al., 2017](#); [Castro et al., 2019](#); [Feng et al., 2020](#); [Jasmine et al., 2020](#); [Melo-Ferraz et al., 2021](#)). In this study, the i-PRF antibacterial effect is not confirmed. As the main components and mechanisms responsible for antibacterial activity are not clearly defined, it is possible that i-PRF cannot maintain its antibacterial activity during rapid freezing at -80°C and thawing processes. In contrast, the i-PRF used in BSSO surgery was fresh and with full antibacterial activity potential. No infectious complications were observed during the follow-up period neither in the test group nor in the control group patients.

It should be noted that the use of the i-PRF in surgery slightly increases surgical time and costs and requires prior knowledge to prepare the i-PRF. Limitations of the study include single-center design, limited sample size, and relatively short follow-up period. There are no articles published about PRF application in BSSO for bone regeneration or correction of mandibular lower border defect. Only one research investigated neurosensory recovery after bilateral sagittal split osteotomy with PRF application ([Tabrizi et al., 2018](#)). This study emphasizes the advantageous properties of i-PRF and its possibilities in cranio-maxillofacial surgery for surgical procedure modification and field development.

The use of i-PRF in BSSO osteotomy sites after a yearlong period increases the bone volume, which is beneficial to reduce the risk of developing mandibular lower border defects. Further investigations are necessary to better understand how to exploit i-PRF in BSSO to minimize bone defect development. The autologous nature, safety aspects, and improvement modification perspectives are all attractive features to entice working with i-PRF. Unanswered questions in this study may encourage surgeons to advance surgical techniques and scientists to create new ideas for material research. Hopefully, these findings will

expand knowledge about i-PRF and will take a step forward for biomaterial standardization. Another method of protein analysis in i-PRF was shown and proven for its usability in i-PRF characterization.

5. Conclusions

Within the limitations of this study, the findings suggest that the application of i-PRF during BSSO may contribute to increased bone formation at the vertical osteotomy site. However, visual assessment of the mandibular lower border did not clearly indicate a noticeable advantage related to the use of i-PRF. The absence of a significant correlation between protein concentrations and net bone volume changes suggests that specific protein levels may not be directly associated with patient healing outcomes. The findings encourage the application of more comprehensive assessment methods in further research and validate the results in a larger patient cohort study.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, methodology, investigation, data curation, writing - original draft preparation, visualisation, L.M.; conceptualization, methodology, investigation, writing - review and editing, I.Sk.; investigation, review and editing, G.S.; review and editing, A.Du.; review and editing, visualisation, K.E.; writing - review and editing, O.R.; review and editing, M.D.; funding acquisition, administration, review and editing, S.V.; review and editing, A.Do.; formal analysis, review and editing, M.Z.; conceptualization, methodology, investigation, supervision, writing - review and editing, supervision, funding acquisition, administration, I.Sa.; All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgements

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No.857287 (BBCE - Baltic Biomaterials Centre of Excellence).

The authors acknowledge financial support from the European Union Recovery and Resilience Facility fund, project No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/1/CFLA/005 RSU internal and RSU with LASE external consolidation.

Data availability

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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